

EPEMCtm Benefits

Ten Reasons to Consider Switching to Extended Plasma-electromagnetic Cosmology

Sf. R. Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM

October 11, 2018

ABSTRACT

EPEMC offers many new facets which are unavailable in BBC and standard PC/EUC. Furthermore it opens an avenue for diffusionist and catastrophist studies which are more reliant upon classical and modern high energy physics at all scales, as well as geology, astrophysics, and thermodynamics. By utilizing comparative mythology and lab-based and field-based research, EPEMC opens wide the span of human history and time for exploration of tantalizing theories, while remaining sensitive to important scientific principles and advancements. In this paper, ten (of many) advantages are listed explaining why an author should utilize the *modular approach* of EPEMC, and how to do so in an ethical and independent manner. The switch can be rather seamless, as the cosmology is already being adopted, piecemeal by the BBC scientific community, and as diffusionism and catastrophism have returned fully into archaeology.

Key words: Plasma cosmology - electromagnetism - diffusionism - uniformitarianism - catastrophism

Top Ten Reasons to consider making a switch.

The acknowledgement of the validity of plasma-electromagnetic cosmology is coming like an avalanche. Already Big Bang Cosmologists (BBC), particularly black hole and dark matter theoreticians, are acknowledging that the electromagnetic vision of the Universe is correct¹. Videographic, documented evidence, laboratory results, and satellite data all concur with a general PEMC. However, the Electric Universe proponents at Thunderbolts Project, and the Plasma Cosmologists of IEEE, do not agree and have failed to control their narrative as a cohesive, alternative cosmology (dating to 1927 as well²) to BBC. Therefore BBC will consume PEMC and try to change the naming conventions and wind up with the same or similar research results. Compare Gabuzda et al...³ with Scott⁴-Thornhill⁵, or with Robitaille⁶-Dowdye⁷, and Juergens⁸. Other comparisons may be found in the author's incredibly detailed overview analysis, "Magnetic Universe Theory."

Furthermore, the work of Talbott-Cardona et al... (by its nature Velikovskian in origin), remains at odds with not only mainstream archaeology/anthropology but with other comparative mythologist currents such as Hancock-West or Sitchin-von Daniken. To make matters more interesting, each alternative current has its own resident expert geologist, such as Carlson, Schoch, and Mungo-Jupp. They must borrow upon the strength of geology as a "hard science." But while TP also utilizes core physics, the other current rely on astronomy and archaeoastronomy, which are on less solid footing. TP/EU is also more comprehensive, but not comprehensive enough.

The author provides a new modular based cosmology for a new generation of researchers. Although reality may have an objective Truth, each research projects have their own subjective hypothetical truths as a sort of canvas upon which to paint their theories, biases, and models. The modular approach to the *Extended* portion of EPEMC enables the researcher to dabble and combine in a natural way, without violating the bounds of the cosmology. Whether it is PEMC_Egyptology or PEMC_Atlantology or PEMC_Viking-diffusion, there is room (with data and citation) for creating extended narratives within the PEMC framework.

There is also a provided extended timeline⁹ which gives *legroom* for evidence-based supposition and chronological variance (given the difficulty of dating rocks, rock art, and the problems of C-14 dating).

These are the top 10 reasons for alternative researchers to consider a switch to EPEMC:

1. Extended chronology (200k years for modern body humans, 40k years for modern consciousness)
2. Respect for religiospiritual research as part of a discussion of mankind's origins and survival
3. Acceptance of a cataclysm+uniformitarian paradigm (stop/start/accelerated/decelerated mechanisms)
4. Modular freedom
5. Lack of political baggage
6. No publishing containers; Occam's Razor is the emphasis¹⁰
7. Support of bleeding edge High Energy Physics results
8. Strong foundational citations by the author
9. Boundless varying projects to fill a very large vessel, plenty of "room" (world not solved).
10. Support of IEEE (via PEMC) and Ancient American (via Diffusionism) and TP (via EU)

¹ See Author's work, "The Predictable Rise of Charged Dark Matter"

² Ibid. Table 1

³ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1712.08414.pdf>

⁴ <http://www.ptep-online.com/2015/PP-41-13.PDF>

⁵ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Kff_ytg0-8w

⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3bQ1zSfbExo>

⁷ https://www.theepochtimes.com/former-nasa-physicist-disputes-einsteins-relativity-theory_739183.html

⁸ http://www.velikovsky.info/Ralph_Juergens

⁹ See Author's work, "On the Origins of Religions," Tables 1 & 2

¹⁰ For example if you are an ancient/alien architect theorist, simply provide reasonable data that is not pseudoscientific in its nature. Such as studies, testimony, textual support, etc...

Basic Framework (How to Switch):

In writing papers, the key is to take a soft-hard position. The openness to the mainstream POV enables the use of geological data, archaeological research, carbon dating, previous scientific work, etc... Meanwhile, by taking a softer stance and being open, one can easily accept new possibilities. Too many scientists become overconfident in one hypothesis and stake their entire careers upon remaining steadfast and attached to that one hypothesis. With EPEMC, this is not required. When doing hard research one simply presents and sticks to a solid, reputable cosmology with the historical backing of 150 years of laboratory research¹¹.

Regarding the papers, a good platform for upload is Academia.edu (host of this paper), Arxiv, Ptep, or ResearchGate. With the latter, more than likely it will require the removal of the most diffusionist and catastrophist elements, but most other data will be acceptable to R^G or Arxiv.

Also, concerning the construction of the papers, they should contain copious citations, especially of a mixture of alternative research and mainstream. If the alternative research relies upon the mainstream, this will make it more difficult to dismiss the research “out of hand.”

When utilizing EPEMC, the author requests that the researcher place a small note at the end of the paper in reference to the author’s original work (as a citation)¹² and refer to EPEMCtm. Separately any other works may also be referred to (or, if necessary, take replace of the original work.)

Format of papers may take any standard form, and utilize any standard citation style (such as APA, etc...) Papers should also be submitted to this author for embedding or linking on the archive.

Conclusion

The EPEMC model as presented in the author’s cited works is openly modular, and while not technically “freeform”, is as freeform as science *should be*. Room to speculate, - to breathe and stretch your proverbial legs - is essential to imaginative exploration, and has been the hallmark of **real science** from Galileo to Newton to Tesla to Hubble. Men (and women) of the past which have been forced into a coercive bubble frequently find their work excessively criticised, with too much politics and personal vendettas clouding and obscuring their work. Its modular design provides not only freedom, but prevents wasted resources by eliminating the need to “reinvent the wheel” and fight for oneself *alone*.

EPEMC as a framework is an unhinged box. You can put whatever you need (if it is supported by physical evidence) into this box, and wrap it up in the packaging needed to present to your audience.

Furthermore it is fresh, and beyond postmodern. By not conforming to tradition peer-review but instead to critically minded but tolerant readership, your work can find a safe haven away from the agendas of politicised and patriarchal journals. Help may even be found to provide publishing and protection, with the author working on specific toolkits to empower the publishers. Meanwhile, despite protections, EPEMC is not protectionist against each other. Individuals are “free to move about the cabin,” and provide unique new perspectives.

¹¹ Both PEMC and BBC goes back to 1927, however PEMC really goes back to 1900 and before. See [9].Table 1

¹² [1]

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